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TEACHER'S TECHNOLOGICAL LITERACY: THE STRENGTH OF EFFECTIVE TEACHING IN THE NEW NORMAL

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The COVID-19 pandemic continuously affects the Department of Education. It caused a lot of changes in the educational system of the country - from the extraction of the curriculum guide into the Most Essential Learning Competencies in each grade level, the grading system, the assessment of learning, the schedule of classes, and most especially the mode of learning delivery from face to face classes into the distance learning delivery mode (LDLDM) which includes online classes, modular-printed, and modular-digital. Now, face-to-face classes have been implemented again, this set-up is now called the new normal.

In the new normal teaching and learning, the role of teachers is very essential in the implementation of the new educational system of the Philippines, because teachers are the conduit of teaching and learning processes to learners. For three years of battling from the virus, teachers are obliged to use different technological platforms like Google Meet, Google Classroom, MS Teams, Zoom, Wikispaces Classroom, Edmodo, DOST Coursewares, PHET Simulations, video clips, etc. for effective teaching and learning happens since there is a great learning gap to learners during the lock down.

During the distance learning delivery mode (LDLDM), the teacher's technological literacy has been developed and becoming the strength of the effective teaching in the new normal. The more technologically literate the teacher is the more effective and efficient he is in teaching, because he has different means that he may use in teaching that will be aligned to the learning styles of the students. As stated by Jamon, et. al., (2021), technologically literate 21st-century teacher is the main resilient point in the new normal in Philippine public education where teachers can apply ICT in teaching the new normal students, do well in learning innovative conferencing using virtual meeting, can use virtual means of communication well, and know how to explore the different use of social media communications and social applications to communicate with the students.

Technological literacy skill of teachers is one of the most important skills that teachers must possess. Without this skill, it is hard for them to sustain effective teaching and learning processes in these new normal days. Teachers who use technology in teaching increase their students' achievement making them motivated and critical

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thinkers, as well as, their metacognition where they learn how to learn and affective domains. Moreover, technological literacy also influences how teachers perceive paper works and lesson planning. Teachers who are not knowledgeable on how to use the technology cannot be fully efficient and effective if they will just rely alone in the printed teaching and learning materials, worst consequence is both teachers and students will suffer and that is where graduating without learning happens.

Therefore, teachers should have proper and enough training and seminar-workshops about the use of different technologies in the teaching and learning process in the new normal. The use of technology during in-service training improves the technological literacy of teachers. Meanwhile, the incorporation of technology in education is really recommended and educational technology must be introduced during the pre-service education because teachers will be better prepared for teaching and learning.

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